

Sequential separation and spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and nickel using α -oximinoacetoacetanilidebenzoylhydrazone

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A rapid method has been developed for sequential separation and extractive spectrophotometric determination of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with α -oximinoacetoacetanilidebenzoylhydrazone (HINABH). HINABH forms a yellow colored complex with Co^{II} , which is extractable into *n*-butanol in the pH range 6.0–7.0 and has λ_{max} at 425 nm; Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.2–5.0 ppm. Ni^{II} forms a yellow colored complex which is extractable into isoamyl alcohol at pH 9.0 and has λ_{max} at 420 nm; Beer's law is obeyed in the range 1–14 ppm. The method has been successfully employed for the analysis of Co and Ni in the real samples and synthetic mixtures.

Several methods have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and nickel but they suffer from various limitations¹. In the present method, HINABH has been used as an analytical reagent for the extraction, sequential separation and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} .

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of cobalt-HINABH and nickel-HINABH complexes against reagent blank showed λ_{max} at 425 and 420 nm, respectively. Optimum pH for the extraction of Co^{II} in *n*-butanol was 6.0 and that for Ni^{II} in isoamyl alcohol was 9.0. The M : L ratio was 1 : 3 for Co-HINABH while 1 : 2 for Ni-HINABH as established by Job's continuous variation and mole-ratio methods. Calibration curves were linear over the concentration range 0.2–5.0 ppm for cobalt and 1–14 ppm for nickel under the optimum conditions. Regression coefficient of correlation values of cobalt and nickel were 0.999 and 0.997, respectively. The molar absorptivities and Sandell sensitivity were $4980 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.01185 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for Co and $2169 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.024 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for Ni, respectively. Ten replicate determinations of sample solutions containing 50 μg of cobalt or nickel gave mean absorbance of 0.22 and 0.42, respectively, with variation from mean at 95% confidence limit as 49.6 ± 0.66 for Co and 50.40 ± 0.69 for Ni.

Interferences : For the interference studies, 20 mg/ml of the anions and 10.0 mg/ml of the cations were added individually for the determination of 50 μg of Co and 100 μg of Ni. It was observed that 20 mg of oxalate, chloride, bro-

midate, acetate, tartarate, fluoride, iodide, sulfate, phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, urea, thiocyanate, chlorate, iodate, bromate and 1 mg of citrate, vanadate did not interfere. EDTA interfered strongly. Similarly, 10 mg of Ca^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mg^{II} , Ba^{II} , Bi^{III} , Zn^{II} , Li^{I} , W^{VI} ; 8 mg of Al^{III} , Mn^{II} ; 5 mg of Ag^{I} , Zr^{IV} ; 1 mg of Hg^{II} , Mo^{VI} , U^{VI} , Cr^{III} did not interfere. EDTA was masked with calcium chloride. Cu^{II} was reduced to Cu^{I} with sodium bisulfite, and Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} were masked with tartarate. The interference due to Pb^{II} was removed by sodium sulfate, whereas Pd^{II} was separated in the acidic range (0.1 *N* H_2SO_4). The tolerance limit was taken as the amount of foreign ion to cause an error of not more than $\pm 2\%$ in the recovery of the metal ions.

The results of determination of Co and Ni in synthetic mixtures and real samples are presented in Table 1.

Sequential separation and spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and nickel : To an aliquot containing 50 μg of Co and 100 μg of Ni, were added 0.5% HINABH (1 ml) and buffer solution (2 ml) of pH 6.0, then diluted with distilled water (10 ml). The cobalt complex was extracted with *n*-butanol (10 ml). The organic phase was shaken for 2 min with 1 *N* HCl (10 ml) for back-extraction of nickel. The absorbance of solution was measured at 425 nm using a reagent blank and the amount of cobalt present was determined. The aqueous phase containing nickel as well as the aqueous phase obtained after back-extraction were combined and analyzed for nickel content (Table 2).

The present method can be applied for spectrophotometric determination and sequential separation of cobalt and nickel in synthetic mixtures and real samples.

Table 1. Determination of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} in real samples and synthetic mixtures

Sample (μg)	Metal(II) : Found ^a	R.S.D.	Reported value
<i>Determination of cobalt :</i>			
Synthetic mixtures :			
(1) Co (50), Pd (50), Cr (100)	50.00	0.06	50.00
(2) Co (50), Pb (50), W (100)	49.80	0.08	50.00
Real samples :			
Vitamin B ₁₂	4.33	1.53	4.34
Co (4.34%)			
<i>Determination of nickel :</i>			
Synthetic mixtures :			
(1) Pd (50), Ni (100), Cu (50)	100.60	0.30	100.00
(2) Co (50), Ni (100), Al (100)	99.30	0.34	100.00
Real sample :			
Stainless steel (bleached wire)			
ITA Lab			
Co, 0.03; S, 0.02; Si, 0.58;	13.80	0.98	13.89
Mn, 1.77; P, 0.036; Cr, 6.47;			
Ni, 13.89; Mo, 2.03%			
^a Average of three determinations.			

Table 2. Sequential separation and spectrophotometric determination of Co^{II} and Ni^{II}

Sl. no.	Amount of metal taken (μg)		Amount of metal found (μg)			
	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	R.S.D.	Ni ^{II}	R.S.D.
1.	50	100	49.30	0.68	101.00	0.57
2.	40	80	40.60	1.64	80.70	0.41
3.	20	40	19.30	1.73	39.00	1.48
4.	10	30	10.70	3.10	28.70	1.16

Experimental

A Baush and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer was used. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used. Cobalt sulfate and nickel sulfate solutions were prepared in distilled water containing small amounts of sulfuric acid and standardized gravimetrically².

α -Oximinoacetoacetanilidebenzoylhydrazone was synthesized by the reported method³. HINABH solution (0.5%) was prepared in dimethylformamide. Ammonium acetate buffer (pH 6.0) and ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer

(pH 9.0) were used for maintaining constant pH.

Determination of Co : To a solution containing 50 μg of Co^{II} was added a 0.5% HINABH in DMF (1 ml), followed by ammonium acetate buffer solution (2 ml) to adjust the pH to 6.0. The volume was made upto 10 ml with distilled water and equilibrated with *n*-butanol (10 ml). The brownish yellow coloured organic phase was separated. Anhydrous sodium sulfate was added to remove traces of water. The absorbance of the organic phase was then measured against the reagent blank at 425 nm.

Determination of Ni : To a solution containing 100 μg of Ni^{II}, was added a 0.5% HINABH solution in DMF (1 ml), followed by ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer solution (2 ml) to adjust the pH to 9.0. The volume was made upto 10 ml with distilled water and equilibrated with isoamyl alcohol (10 ml). The yellow coloured organic phase was separated. Anhydrous sodium sulfate was added to remove traces of water. The absorbance of the organic phase was measured against the reagent blank at 420 nm.

Solutions of vitamin B₁₂ and stainless steel samples were prepared according to the standard procedures⁴.

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